

A Machine Learning Approach to Exploring Gross Revenues of Movies

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Abstract

In this paper, I use a machine learning approach to explore the impact of movie recognition such as the number of award nominations/wins and reviews by critics and viewers on gross revenue. I find that movie ratings by critics and viewers are positively correlated and that the ratings are positively correlated with gross revenue. The correlation between gross revenue and number of IMDB votes is 0.6, suggesting that ratings by critics and viewers are a good predictor of gross revenue. On the other hand, there is a weak positive correlation between ratings and award nominations and wins, suggesting that movie recognition is not a good predictor of gross revenue. The summary of the findings is that movies with excellent reviews are the ones with high gross revenue, but it may not be the case for movies that receive many award nominations and wins.

Keywords: Learning approach, Gross Revenue

INTRODUCTION

The movie industry is a booming business. Billions of dollars of revenues are generated worldwide each year. However, the success of each movie can be surprising or even unpredictable. In this paper, I explore the various factors related gross revenue of movies and use machine learning to build models that capture the relationships between these factors.

I build least squares linear regression models to examine the relationships between factors such as a number of award nominations/wins and user/critic ratings and gross revenue. Overall, I find a positive relationship between gross revenue and award nominations and wins. I also find positive relationships between ratings given by critics and users.

Past research includes a paper by Ainslie et al. (2005) who find a significant impact on actors and directors on which movies consumers decide to watch. Cachon and Lariviere (2005) find that revenue sharing would determine supply chain decisions with retailers in the movie industry. Cai et al. (2012) study the impact of channels and revenue sharing decisions and found that bargaining deals would benefit all agents in the supply chain. Sood and Dreze (2006) analyze movie sequel and found that sequels with numbers in the titles would increase viewer satisfaction because it induces more similarity with the parent movie. Dellarocas et al. (2010) find that consumers prefer to publish reviews of movies that are less available and have received ratings below average.

METHODS

I use a dataset with basic information of movies such as title, year and date of release, genre, language, country, number of award nominations and wins, user ratings, and critics ratings. The sources include IMDb (Internet Movie Database) and Rotten Tomatoes. Table 1 shows the variables in the dataset and an example. There are 40,000 movies in the dataset in total. I clean the data by removing mismatches between Year and Released Date, do not remove more than 10% of the dataset. The final data includes 34,168 movies.

Variable	Example
Title	The Peanuts Movie
Year	2015
Released Date	11/6/2015
Genre	Animation, Adventure, Comedy
Language	English
Country	USA
Awards	Nominated for 1 Golden Globe. Another 1 win & 43 nominations.
Metascore	67
imdbRating	7.2
imdbVotes	27426
imdbID	tt2452042
Type	Movie
tomatoMeter	87
tomatoImage	certified
tomatoRating	7.1
tomatoReviews	174
tomatoFresh	151
tomatoRotten	23
tomatoUserMeter	77
tomatoUserRating	3.9
tomatoUserReviews	66226
Production	20th Century Fox
Budget	99000000
Gross Revenue	244778411

Table 1. Variables in Dataset and An Example

To process the awards data, I first inspect the ‘Awards’ column, looking for structure in the data. For wins, the data is recorded as ‘Won x’, ‘x wins’, or ‘x win’. I first convert each row in ‘Awards’ into a list of strings. I then convert ‘wins’ to ‘win’ and ‘Won’ to ‘won’ so there are two words in the data associated with wins in a structured way. I look for the index of the string ‘win’ or ‘won’ in each row in ‘Awards’. If ‘win’ is found, I take the previous element in the list, which is the number of wins. If ‘won’ is found, I take the following element, which is also the number of wins. I then add up the two numbers. For nominations, I use a similar approach. I convert ‘nominations’ to ‘nomination’ and ‘Nominated for’ to ‘nominated’. I look for the index of the string ‘nomination’ or ‘nominated’ in each row in ‘Awards’. If ‘nomination’ is found, I take the previous element in the list, which is the number of nominations. If ‘nominated’ is found, I take the following element, which is also the number of nominations. I then add up the two numbers, which gives the total number of nominations not resulting in a win. Therefore, I also add the result to number of wins to get the total nominations the movie received. I assign 0 to all ‘NA’ values.

For modeling, I build a least square linear regression model to explore the relationships between user and critic ratings; award wins and nominations, and gross revenue. I also calculate the Pearson correlation score between these variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 and 2 show the relationship between gross revenue and number of wins and nominations respectively. There is a positive relationship between these variables, so the more awards nominated and won, the higher the gross revenue of a movie. Figure 3 shows the correlation between gross revenue and awards nominations and wins. Gross revenue has a moderate positive correlation with both number of awards won (0.31) and nominations received (0.36). As gross revenue increases, number of awards won and nominations received increases.

Fig. 1: Gross Revenue vs. Number of Wins

Fig. 2: Gross Revenue vs. Number of Nominations

Fig. 3: Pairwise Relationships Between Gross Revenue, Award Wins, and Nominations

There are several variables that describe ratings, including IMDB ratings (IMDB rating represents average user ratings and imdbVotes represents the number of user ratings), and multiple Rotten Tomatoes ratings (represented by several variables pre-fixed by tomato). I investigate the pairwise relationships between these different descriptors using graphs. Figure 4 shows the distribution and means of user and critic ratings. Figure 5 shows the pairwise relationships between IMDB and Rotten Tomatoes ratings. IMDB ratings (IMDB rating) and Rotten Tomatoes ratings (tomatoRating) both have bell-shaped curves. Both ratings have similar medians (6.4 and 6.0) and means (6.2 and 5.9). They also have a positive correlation of 0.8. One difference is that Rotten Tomatoes ratings have a wider inter-quartile range than IMDB user ratings. Another difference is that IMDB user ratings have more low scores (below 4 out of 10) than Rotten Tomatoes ratings. This could come from users who really do not like the movies. There are fewer such critics on Rotten Tomatoes.

Fig. 4: Distribution and Means of User and Critic Ratings

Fig. 5: Pairwise Relationships Between IMDB and Rotten Tomatoes Ratings

The user and critic ratings typically reflect the general appeal of the movie to the public or gather opinions from a larger body of critics. Whereas awards are given by professional societies that may evaluate a movie on specific attributes, such as artistic performance, screenplay, sound design, etc. I study the relationship between ratings and awards using graphs (awards here refers to wins and/or nominations). Figure 6 shows the correlation between number of award nominations and user and critic ratings. Figure 7 shows the correlation between number of award wins and user and critic ratings. The ratings have moderate to low correlations (between 0.2 and 0.4) with the number of awards won and nominations. The scatterplots show high variation in number of awards won and nominations especially for the upper half of each rating’s scale. The ratings would provide mediocre predictions of the success of a movie in winning awards or nominations.

Fig. 6: Correlation Between Award Nominations and User and Critic Ratings

Fig. 7: Correlation Between Award Wins and User and Critic Ratings

Figure 8 shows the relationship between gross revenue and number of votes. There is a high correlation between gross revenue and number of IMDB votes (0.6). This is expected because high gross revenue implies that more people have watched the movie, so it is likely to receive more votes and reviews, whether good or bad. There is a high correlation between domestic and total gross revenue (0.9). This is expected because a successful movie in the domestic market should extend to the global market, considering that people’s tastes are vastly similar across the globe, especially in a global industry like the movie industry. Figure 9 shows the correlation between ratings and budget. There is a very low correlation (close to 0) between budget and any type of ratings. This may be counter-intuitive at first because one might assume that more budget would be spent on producing higher quality movies that receive higher ratings. However, in reality, much money is not spent wisely and wasted. A successful movie not only depends on the budget but also on the quality of the production team, script, direction, etc. Therefore, high-budgeted movies do not guarantee high ratings.

Fig. 8: Gross Revenue vs. Number of Votes

Fig. 9: Correlation Between Ratings and Budget

CONCLUSION

This paper shows the use of an ordinary least squares linear regression, a machine learning approach, to examine the relationship between gross revenue, award nominations and wins, and reviews by users and critics. Positive relationships are found between these variables. Number of votes is also positively correlated with gross revenue. The results can be useful for predicting the success of movies by monitoring the reviews by users and critics shortly after the movies are released. If the reviews are favorable, the movie will likely generate high revenue. On the other hand, budget is not correlated with ratings, which should warn movie producers that spending excessive budget does not always translate into high revenue. Future extension may include exploring the factors that contribute to the success of movies. This study already excludes budget from the success of movies. The next question is to examine what actually creates a successful movie.

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